

Studies in the Cycloheptane Series. Part—XXXI : Friedel-Crafts Reaction of the Anhydride of $\alpha\alpha$ -Dimethylglutaric Acid with Different Aromatic Hydrocarbons and Synthesis of 1,1-Dimethyl-3,4-benzo / substituted benzocycloheptanes and 1,1-Dimethylthieno [3,4-b] cycloheptane

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The anhydride of $\alpha\alpha$ -dimethylglutaric acid on condensation with benzene, toluene, isomeric xylenes, chlorobenzene, anisole, tetralin, naphthalene and thiophene under F. C. conditions gives the respective $\alpha\alpha$ -dimethyl- γ -aroyl- n -butyric acids which on Clemmensen reduction yield δ -aryl- n -valeric acids. These on cyclisation with PPA furnish III and IV (X=O) which on Clemmensen reduction give the respective hydrocarbons (III and IV : X=H₂).

FRIEDEL-Crafts reaction involving the anhydride of $\beta\beta$ -disubstituted glutaric acids¹ has been extensively studied but similar reaction using substitution in the α -position has hardly been reported. To study the behaviour of the opening of such an anhydride, $\alpha\alpha$ -dimethylglutaric acid² [NMR-(CDCl₃): 1.2 δ (6H, s, CH₃); 1.8 δ (2H, t, CH₂ β to COOH); 2.4 δ (2H, t, CH₂COOH); 11.6 δ (2H, s, COOH)] has been prepared by simultaneous oxidation and hydrolysis of 4-cyano-2,2-dimethylbutyraldehyde [NMR(CDCl₃): 1.1 δ (6H, s, CH₃), 1.9 δ (2H, t, CH₂ β to CN), 2.3 δ (2H, t, CH₂CN), 9.8 δ (1H, s, CHO)] and its anhydride condensed with different aromatic substrates to give $\alpha\alpha$ -dimethyl- γ -aroyl- n -butyric acids (I). Structures were confirmed by NaOBr oxidation to known aromatic acids, uv (footnote to Table 1) and ir (two $>C=O$ absorptions in the range 1720-1670 cm⁻¹) spectral studies. The possibility of the formation of the keto-acid (II) was ruled out on the basis of the work of Rothstein³, according to which it was not possible to get a keto-acid from the anhydride or acid chloride derived from the tertiary acids. Additional support was lent by the

nmr spectra of the keto-acids. The nmr spectrum of the parent acid (HOOC-CH₂-CH₂-C(CH₃)₂-COOH)

showed CH₂COOH signal at 2.4 δ , whereas CH₂-CO in the keto-acids (I) (footnote Table 1) appeared in the range 2.97-3.1 δ showing a considerable downfield shift. Furthermore, 2,4-DNPs of the keto-acids in this case were formed readily and in very good yields in comparison to those obtained from $\beta\beta$ -dimethylglutaric acid anhydrides and this might be due to the steric effect in the latter.

The keto-acids on Clemmensen reduction gave the corresponding $\alpha\alpha$ -dimethyl- δ -aryl- n -valeric acids which on cyclisation with PPA furnished the corresponding cyclic ketones (III and IV : X=O) and these on reduction finally gave the corresponding hydrocarbons (III and IV : X=H₂).

Experimental

$\alpha\alpha$ -Dimethyl- γ -aroyl- n -butyric acid : $\alpha\alpha$ -Dimethylglutaric acid anhydride (0.03 mol) on condensation with dry hydrocarbon (30 ml) in the presence of anhydrous AlCl₃ (0.06 mol) at 0-5° and working up in the customary manner gave the keto-acid in 80-85% yield.

TABLE 1— $\alpha\alpha$ -DIMETHYL- γ -AROYL- n -BUTYRIC ACIDS

Sl. No.	Aroyl	m.p. °C/ b.p. °C/mm	n_D^{25}	2,4-DNP, m.p. °C
1.	Benzoyl ^a	195/8	1.5144	191
2.	4-Methylbenzoyl	85	—	215
3.	3,4-Dimethylbenzoyl	72	—	193
4.	2,4-Dimethylbenzoyl	156/2	1.5213	240
5.	2,5-Dimethylbenzoyl	155/3	1.5432	148
6.	4-Methoxybenzoyl ^b	90	—	160
7.	4-Chlorobenzoyl	150/7	1.5983	201
8.	1-Naphthoyl ^c	108	—	252
9.	5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-naphthoyl ^d	140/8	1.5214	202
10.	2-Thenoyl ^e	131	—	249

a: $\lambda_{\max}$ 240 nm (ϵ 248^{*}); b: $\lambda_{\max}$ 270 nm (276.5^{*}); ¹H nmr (CDCl₃): 1.8 δ (6H, s, CH₃); 2.0 δ (2H, t, CH₂-CH₂CO-); 2.97 δ (2H, t, CH₂CO); 3.85 δ (8H, s, OCH₃); 6.9 δ (2H, d, Ar protons); 11.5 δ (1H s, COOH); c: $\lambda_{\max}$ 245 nm ($\epsilon_{\max}$ 46510); nmr (CDCl₃ + TFA): 1.3 δ (6H, s, CH₃); 2.1 δ (2H, t, CH₂-CH₂CO-); 3.1 δ (2H, t, CH₂CO); 7.2-8.2 δ (7H, b, m, Ar protons); d: $\lambda_{\max}$ 260 nm (248^{*}); e: $\lambda_{\max}$ 260 nm (260^{*}); (ϵ 10040); nmr (CDCl₃ + TFA): 1.3 δ (6H, s, CH₃); 2.0 δ (2H, t, CH₂CH₂-C=O); 3.0 δ (2H, t, CH₂CO); 7.1-7.8 δ (3H, b, m, Ar protons).

All the $\lambda_{\max}$ values are in ethanol.

* These $\lambda_{\max}$ values correspond to the parent acetophenones.

TABLE 2— $\alpha\alpha$ -DIMETHYL- δ -ARYL- n -VALERIC ACIDS

Sl. No.	Aryl	b.p. °C/m	n_D^{25}	S-Benzyl- isothiuronium salt, m.p. °C
1.	Phenyl	145/8	1.5124	140
2.	4-Methylphenyl	140/10 ⁻¹	1.5014	104
3.	3,4-Dimethylphenyl	165/8	1.5014	118
4.	2,4-Dimethylphenyl	192/1	1.5049	126
5.	2,5-Dimethylphenyl	200/7	1.5114	106
6.	4-Methoxyphenyl	182/0.5	1.5165	119
7.	4-Chlorophenyl	156/5	1.5284	148
8.	1-Naphthoyl	192/10 ⁻¹	1.5231	130
9.	5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-naphthoyl	180/8	1.5318	122
10.	2-Thenoyl	130/5	1.4865	127

TABLE 3—1,1-DIMETHYL-3,4-BENZO/SUBSTITUTED BENZOCYCLOHEPTAN-2-ONES

Sl. No.	Substituent	b.p. °C/mm	n_D^{25}	2,4-DNP, m.p. °C
1.	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H	125/1	1.5174	152
2.	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₄ =CH ₃	185/8	1.5214	230
3.	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₄ =CH ₂	110/10 ⁻²	1.5303	211
4.	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₄ =CH ₂	99/3	1.5345	144
5.	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₄ =CH ₂	148/3	1.5334	126
6.	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₄ =OCH ₃	110/1	1.5403	214
7.	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₄ =Cl	114/10 ⁻¹	1.4945	232
8.	R ₁ =R ₂ =H; R ₃ R ₄ =	137/10 ⁻¹	1.5384	191
9.	R ₁ =R ₂ =H; R ₃ R ₄ =(CH ₂) ₄ ^a	129/1	1.5668	156
10.	Thieno [3,4-b] ^b	112/10 ⁻²	1.4743	160

a: $\lambda_{\max}$ 255 nm (EtOH); b: $\lambda_{\max}$ 255 nm (EtOH)

TABLE 4—1,1-DIMETHYL-3,4-BENZO/SUBSTITUTED BENZOCYCLOHEPTANES

Sl. No.	Substituent	b.p. °C/mm	n_D^{25}
1.	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H	140/10 ⁻¹	1.5404
2.	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₄ =CH ₃	132/10 ⁻¹	1.4552
3.	R ₁ =R ₂ =H; R ₃ =R ₄ =CH ₃	98/3	1.5373
4.	R ₁ =R ₂ =H; R ₃ =R ₄ =CH ₂	125/1	1.5244
5.	R ₁ =R ₂ =H; R ₃ =R ₄ =CH ₂	174/10 ⁻¹	1.5323
6.	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₄ =OCH ₃	175/1	1.5315
7.	R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₄ =Cl	95/10 ⁻¹	1.4014
8.	R ₁ =R ₂ =H; R ₃ R ₄ =	155/10 ⁻²	1.5814
9.	R ₁ =R ₂ =H; R ₃ R ₄ =(CH ₂) ₄	135/10 ⁻²	1.5583
10.	Thieno [3,4-b]	140/1	1.5444

$\alpha\alpha$ -Dimethyl- δ -aryl- n -valeric acid: The above keto-acid (0.015 mol) was reduced with Zn/Hg (40 g) and conc. HCl (100 ml), (60 hr); conc. HCl (5 ml) being added after every 6 hr. On normal work up, the reduced acid was obtained.

1, 1-Dimethyl-3, 4-benzo/substituted benzocycloheptan-2-one: The above acid (0.009 mol) was heated with PPA (15 g P₂O₅ in 10 ml H₃PO₄) at 180-90° for 2 hr and the reaction mixture on working up gave III (X=O) or IV (X=O) in 55-60% yield.

1, 1-Dimethyl-3, 4-benzo/substituted benzocycloheptane: The cyclic ketone (0.004 mol) was reduced with Zn/Hg (20 g) and conc. HCl (60 ml) (60 hr). Conc. HCl (5 ml) was added after every 6 hr and on working up, the reaction mixture gave III (X=H₂) or IV (X=H₂).

The different products obtained above are shown in Tables 1 to 4. All the compounds in the tables gave satisfactory C and H analysis.

References

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